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Abstract. The translation of this article deals with transformation, its types, pragmatic features of lexical transformations and their presentation in Uzbek, the methods of their translation. It is a requirement of the time to be aware of the economic, social and political news taking place in the world at the moment, and taking into account its pragmatic features therefore, there is a need to translate the materials in English into Uzbek.

Key words: transformation, lexical transformation, syntactic changes, analogical translation, synonyms, antonyms, explanatory translation, transcription, transliteration.

It should be noted that today English has become the language of international relations. As Uzbekistan integrates into the world community, the importance of the English language in the country is also increasing. Also, international network (internet) materials, many scientific and technical news can be found in English. It has become necessary for us to learn English not only for science and technology news that can contribute to the development of our country, for international communication, but also to inform about the history of our country, our great ancestors, and to promote our traditions and culture. Therefore, the importance of English in the field of education has increased.

In accordance with this, it is today's demand that future translators should be fully aware of the secrets of science, such as language and culture, the specific nature of the language, lexicon, translator's speech, along with the knowledge and skills related to the field of translation.

We consider translation to be a multifaceted activity that requires a lot of knowledge and a lot of work. Translation scientist I. Zinger says: "A translator must be a careful reader, an excellent stylist, a master of words, a psychologist, and knowledgeable in all aspects."

Thus, the translator uses various changes (transformations).

The most important of them are:

1. Changing the word order;**2. Various lexical substitutions:**

A) replacement with synonymous words; B) replacement with antonyms;

V) replacing one word group with another word group; D) to give a full translation of words with abbreviations or vice versa, because there is no such abbreviation in the translated language (it cannot be UK-YUK or BK, because there is no such abbreviation, so read UK United Kingdom entered);

3. Syntactic changes (transformations):

A) translate a compound sentence with a simple sentence;

B) turning a simple sentence into a compound sentence;

V) replacing the main clause with a subordinate clause;

- G) giving the subordinate clause with a conjunction;
 D) turn an equally connected clause with a subordinate clause;
 E) to turn a clause with a subordinate clause through an equal clause.

4. Syntactic changes (transformations) in analogical translation:

- a) turn a simple sentence into a simple sentence;
 b) turning a compound sentence into a compound sentence;

5. Syntactic changes in antonymic translation:

A) giving the participle in the source language in the antonymic form in the translated language (that is, the participle form through the formless form);

6. Syntactic changes in synonymous translation

- a) giving the means in the source language through more than one means of synonymy;

7. Compensation (compensation);

8. Additions (appropriate additions, inappropriate additions);

9. Omissions (necessary and unnecessary omissions);

10. Copying (copying, copying, transcription, transliteration);

We will consider the above changes (transformations) separately below. This type of transformation is clearly visible in the change of word order in the source language during the translation of sentences built according to the laws of one language into another.

For example: I have read her letter

1 2 3 4

When we translate this sentence into Uzbek, its existing word order changes, that is, according to the rules of the translation language, the word order must be reflected in the translation. For example: I finished reading his letter.

1 3 4 2

Thus, we see that the word order in the source language is SVO, while the word order in the translated language is SOV. This shows that both languages belong to different typological groups.

If the source language and the translated language belong to the same typological group (relative), then the word order does not change.

Compare:

I have read her letter 1 2 3 4

Я прочитал ее письмо 1 2 3 4

Therefore, this transformation is not used in practice when dealing with related or typologically close languages, but rather it is carried out through other transformations.

2. Various lexical substitutions:

a) replacement with synonymous words

My parents are workers - Mening avlodlarim ishchilar.

I have seen the lass (pari, qiz) - Men bu qizni (parini, nozanin, go'zal narsani, parivash, go'zal malikani, suluvni) ko'rganman.

b) replacement with antonyms:

He is young - U qari emas.

He is no fool - U aqli.

c) replacement with other word groups:

He likes books. His hobby is boxing

(noun) (gerund)

He likes to read books. (action name)

His field of interest is boxing (noun).

3. Syntactic transformations:

A) translate a compound sentence with a simple sentence:

I came here so that (in order that)

I might study. (sub. clause of purpose)

I came here to study (to study). (simple extended sentence)

B) giving a simple sentence through a compound sentence:

I came in order to study here (simple ext. sentence)

I came here to study. (subordinate clause of purpose) V) replacing the main clause with a subordinate clause and vice versa:

While I was eating my eggs these two strangers came in. I was eating my eggs when these two strangers came in.

I was eating dumplings when two strangers entered.

When I was eating dumplings, two strangers came in.

G) replacing an equally connected clause with a subordinate clause. The girl was standing by the machine and the boy was playing in the yard. The boy was playing in the yard while the girl was standing in front of the car.

He was so busy and that kept him at home.

He was very busy so he was stuck at home.

Analog translation:

4. Sodda gapni sodda gap orqali o'g'irish:

The man is very fond of hunting. Bu odam juda ham ovga ishqiboz.

5. Qo'shma gapni qo'shma gap bilan o'g'irish:

I have not seen him since I met him last

Men uni oxirgi marta uchratdan bo'lsam o'shandan beri ko'rganim yo'q.

Hit the iron while it's hot - Temirni qizig'ida bos.

6. Antonomic translation

He is old - U yosh emas. He is young - U qari emas. He is no fool - U aqli.

7. Synonymous translation

I came to study here - Men bu yerga o'qigani (o'qish uchun, o'qish maqsadida o'qish maqsadi bilan o'qiyman deb, o'qishni deb) keldim.

8. Compensation (compensation):

This is where the shoe pinches - Вот, где собака зарыта - Mana gap qayerda (ekan).

Paddle your own canoe - O'z aravangni tort.

I hate movies - Men kinoni o'lguday yomon ko'raman.

9. Qo'shishlar (o'rinli qo'shishlar):

It is the means of Livelihood (S. Maugham) - Ha endi, (nima ham derdingiz) tirikchilikda.

Look, you haven't seen him as yet? - Hoy, menga qara (bu deyman) sen uni ko'rmadingmi?

10. Omissions:

He put his hands into his pockets - U qo'llarini cho'ntaklariga soldi.

The city of London is any of oldest one in Great Britain - London Angliyadagi eng qadimgi shaharlaridan biri.

Speedo-meter-spidometr

Machine - mashina

Pilaff (pilou) - plov

Peasant -dehqon – dexkan

Collective farm - kolxoz

Paranjan -paranji - parandji

12. Izohli tarjima:

This type of translation is used when it is not possible to directly translate the source language into the translation language, i.e. an interpretive translation (explanation) is provided.

The Nato general gave a greenlight to the military actions in Afganistan -Nato generali Afg'onistondagi harbiy harakatlarga katta yo'l ochib berdi.

The process of making the transition from the language units of the original to the translation units with the help of transformation is called translatability (interlingual) transformation. If we pay attention to the word transformation, this word is derived from the Latin word transformatio to change, means to replace.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the study of equivalence levels and translation transformations in the translation process through English, Russian, and Uzbek texts will help future translators to study the general laws of the translation process in detail, what semantic, they learn that stylistic functions should be taken into account and what rules should be observed both theoretically and practically. In-depth acquisition of knowledge about translation transformations helps to observe the laws of preservation of unity of form and content in translation, author's style in translation.

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